

The box without walls

Sydney Ernest Grimm*

The universe seems to originate from some kind of a singularity and phenomena at the smallest scale size are thought to be about 10^{20} bigger than the supposed metric of the universe (Planck length). Both rare ideas don't rhyme with the supposed configuration of reality. It questions when we have missed the boat.

Introduction

Philosophy of the mathematical nature of reality is about the mathematical framework that underlies the existence of the universe like we know it. That is not a new idea because the ancient Greek philosopher and mathematician [Parmenides of Elea](#) (about 500 B.C.) was the first known scientist who described the concept of an underlying creating reality that envelopes the whole universe. The [Achilles Paradox](#) of his student [Zeno of Elea](#) confirms that Parmenides' concept of an underlying reality had a metric.

In 2008 [Max Tegmark](#) published “*The Mathematical Universe*”.^[1] In the paper Max Tegmark brings the concept of an underlying mathematical reality into live again: “*I explore physics implications of the External Reality Hypothesis (ERH) that there exists an external physical reality completely independent of us humans. I argue that with a sufficiently broad definition of mathematics, it implies the Mathematical Universe Hypothesis (MUH) that our physical world is an abstract mathematical structure.*”

Philosophy about the mathematical nature of reality is an interdisciplinary subject that needs at least philosophy, mathematics and physics. Not at least because some scientists have the idea that during experiments physicists measure absolute properties. But that is an error because we can only measure mutual relations between phenomena. The confusion has an origin: physicists have standardised the mutual relations with the help of [measurement units](#) (e.g. the [International System of units](#)).

The consequence is that reality shows itself with the help of mutual relations. We don't experience absolute properties. Mutual relations are compositions of variable properties otherwise our universe cannot change (transform) at all. But this is a strange idea because if everything is vari-

able why do we have universal constants, like Planck's constant and the constant speed of light? And why are all the changes in relation to energy and momentum conserved too?

It is reasonable to hypothesize that all the variable properties in our universe have a direct relation with non-variable properties. Otherwise the existence of physics laws and constants is hard to imagine.

The hypothesis that there exist non-variable properties – properties we are not aware of in daily life – implies that there must be a non-observable reality too. An underlying reality that is omnipresent in the universe because universal constants exist also everywhere within the volume of the universe.

Suppose it is possible to determine the underlying properties of the universe with the help of reasoning and what we know about the mutual relations between the phenomena (experimental physics). Because there is no method to determine and describe stuff we cannot observe and detect. The consequence is that we can only describe these absolute properties with the help of mathematics.

In other words, Max Tegmark's external reality hypothesis (ERH) – the existence of an external physical reality completely independent of us humans – is not in line with the idea that our physical world is an abstract mathematical structure. Because we are part of the same mathematical structure. The mathematical properties of the underlying non-observable reality determine all the changes in the universe, so it *seems* for us to be an external reality.

The Box without walls

Reality is a concept that has its origin in the sensory perceptions of man. That is why there are different interpretations of reality. For example, reality is everything we can observe. Or reality is everything that can be detected. The consequence of different interpretations of reality is that the scope of the mathematical nature of reality is uncertain. So we need some consensus about the meaning of the term “reality”.

If the universe is like a box without walls, reality is about the contents of the box. Unfortunately most sciences are determining the contents of the box and their mutual relations. So we need another approach to determine what is reality.

Suppose we can move everything we can observe and detect and next we push "all the stuff" together. The result is an enormous "ball" of observable and detectable phenomena. However, we have separated the observable and detectable phenomena from their natural environment. This simplifies the question about the scope of the term *reality*.

I have drawn an image that represents the 4 possibilities (A, B, C, D) to determine the scope of reality in relation to the volume of the universe. Everything that is part of reality is grey rasterised and everything that is not part of reality is transparent.

Possibility B represents the point of view in classic physics: phenomena and their influence are real. Possibility A implies that nothing is part of reality and possibility C is really weird for us. Possibility D envelopes A, B and C so it is not difficult to conclude that if we talk about reality and its mathematical nature we are talking about the whole volume of the universe. In line with the teachings of Parmenides of Elea.

figure 1

The belief that reality is equal to the whole volume of the universe has consequences. Because if all the observable and detectable phenomena and the remaining volume of the universe are part of the same reality, there must be a shared mechanism everywhere within the volume of the universe that is responsible for the "creation" of reality.

But a shared mechanism means that the volume of the universe has dynamical properties. That means that the volume has a structure. Because without a structure the whole volume of the universe is homogeneous and static (no transformations).

It isn't difficult to imagine that the volume of the universe has a structure. We don't know much about the properties of the structure but one thing is for sure: the structure must

be build up of units. The consequence is that the volume of the universe is build up by units with a volume. Figure 2 shows a volume (large cube) that is build up by smaller volumes (small cubes). Together these small volumes create a metric (ℓ_c) within the large cube.

figure 2

Although figure 2 represents a geometrical structure, it isn't a dynamical geometrical structure. That means that the units of the structure have no variable properties. Nevertheless, the small cubes are identical so if there are variable properties all the units can transform continuously because no unit is dominant in relation to the other units around.

If the shape of a unit in the large cube changes – for example with the help of rotation – the unit will destroy the metric (ℓ_c) of the other units of the cube. More worse, the rotating unit creates volume that isn't part of the volume of the universe.

Although figure 2 is just a representation of a hypothetical primitive geometry of the universe, the image shows that the existence of an underlying dynamical structure has mathematical consequences. Because all the transformations of the shapes of the units must be synchronised. Moreover, the amount of change of every unit must be the same otherwise the synchronisation of the transformation of the shape of every unit is impossible. And last but not least, the mechanism that is responsible for the transformation of the shape of the unit has to be equal for every unit of the structure.

The transformation of the shape of every unit under invariant volume is the only way to create variance within the whole structure. In other words, the volume of every unit is invariant and the (shared) surface area of every unit is variable. Now the question is if the schematic dynamical geometry of the volume of the universe is in line with the basic concepts in physics.

In 1901 Max Planck published “*On the Law of Distribution of Energy in the Normal Spectrum*”.^[2] He described that the energy of black body radiation is quantized ($E = h \nu$). The fixed amount of energy – now termed the Planck constant (h) – multiplied with the frequency (ν) of the radiation represents the energy (E) of the emitted electromagnetic wave.

A couple of years later Albert Einstein published the theory of *Special relativity* (1905). He postulated that the speed of light in vacuum (c) is the same for all observers, regardless of the motion of the light source or the motion of the observer.

Both discoveries resulted in the Planck-Einstein relation:

$$E = h \nu = h \frac{c}{\lambda} \rightarrow h \frac{c}{n \ell_c}$$

(λ = wave length; n = multiple; ℓ_c = metric)

The Planck-Einstein relation shows that the equation has only (multiplied) universal constants, except the wave length of the electromagnetic wave (λ). But the Planck-Einstein relation is about the relational properties of the universe (phenomenological physics).

The consequence is that the wave length of an electromagnetic wave is a multiple (n) of a universal constant of length (ℓ_c).^[3] But electromagnetic waves arrive from every direction in space. So it is reasonable to conclude that the hypothetical constant of length (ℓ_c) represents the structure of the *grains of volume* of the universe. Comparable with the schematic image in figure 2.

The theory of Special relativity describes the equivalence of matter and energy because matter represents a local concentration of free energy ($E = m c^2$). The equation shows that free energy (E) represents (quantised) surface area, the square of the speed of light (c^2). Actually, the variable property of the unit of quantised space.

With the help of figure 2 I can state that the speed of light is the number of units of the structure of space that linear propagates 1 quantum of energy during 1 second. In other words, the equivalence of matter and energy describes that free energy shows itself as (a multiple of) a fixed amount of joint surface area.

The invariant volume of every unit of the structure is in line with the experiments. If we accelerate a particle the

increase of velocity doesn't result in an increase of the volume of the particle. In quantum field theory (QFT) particles are created by the structure of the basic quantum fields, actually a rest frame.^[4]

Conclusion:

The change of the shape of every unit of the structure of the volume of the universe – see schematic figure 2 – can be described as 3D *topological* objects under continuous transformation (a type of *homeomorphism*). So it is difficult to argue that it is impossible to determine the dynamical geometry of reality.

The idea that the volume of our universe has a dynamical structure is in line with basic concepts that describe the propagation of free energy in space and the equivalence of matter and energy. Basic concepts that were widely known in the first half of the 20th century.

References:

1. Max Tegmark (2008); “*The Mathematical Universe*”. Foundations of Physics 38: 101-150, 2008. DOI: 10.1007/s10701-007-9186-9 <https://arxiv.org/abs/0704.0646>
 2. Max Planck (1901); “*Ueber das Gesetz der Energy verteilung in Normal spectrum*” Annalen der Physik 309 (3): 553-563 <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19013090310> (English)
 3. Sabine Hossenfelder (2013); “*Minimal length scale scenarios for quantum gravity*.” See “A minimal history”, page 5. Living Reviews in Relativity, January 2013. DOI: 10.12942/lrr-2013-2. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1203.6191>
 4. Art Hobson (2013); “*There are no particles, there are only fields*”. American journal of physics 81, 211. DOI: 10.1119/1.4789885. <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1204/1204.4616.pdf>
- * City of Amersfoort, the Netherlands
email: sydneyernestgrimm@gmail.com
orcid: 0000-0002-2882-420X